

Analysing the Correlation between Physical Activity Levels and Mental Health in Senior Citizens across Different Socio-Economic Groups

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Abstract:

Background: Due to the world's ageing population, geriatric mental health is a serious public health issue. Several research have demonstrated that exercise improves mental health, but few have examined how different socioeconomic groups of older people benefit. This study examines the association among geriatric physical exercise and mental health using socioeconomic factors.

Methods: A retrospective cross-sectional study of 150 community-dwelling persons aged 60 and older was conducted. A convenience sample identified neighbouring community centre participants. We measured mental health with the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), Generalised Anxiety Disorder 7 (GAD-7), and WHO-5 Well-being Index, and physical activity with the IPAQ. Socioeconomic status was determined by income, education, and employment. We employed analysis of variance (ANOVA) to compare socioeconomic groups and Pearson correlation coefficients to examine exercise and mental health.

Results: Participants' mental health improved with more activity. Physical activity reduced anxiety (GAD-7: Mean = 5.8, SD = 2.9), depressive symptoms (GDS: Mean = 6.3, SD = 3.2), and overall well-being (WHO-5: Mean = 14.2, SD = 5.1). Higher socioeconomic groups were associated with greater mental health and increased physical activity, demonstrating that socioeconomic status strongly predicts these outcomes.

Conclusion: Socioeconomic factors strongly affect geriatric physical activity and mental health, and increasing physical activity improves mental health. Increasing physical activity, especially among the poor, may improve senior mental health. Future research should examine the long-term effects of exercise on mental health and socioeconomic inequality intervention strategies.

Keywords: Depression, Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), General Anxiety Disorder 7 (GAD-7), Mental Health, Physical Activity, Socio-Economic Status, Senior Citizens, WHO-5 Well-being Index.

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Introduction

As the world's population grows, older mental health concerns have grown. Depression, anxiety, and cognitive impairment affect older adults' well-being and quality of life.

The WHO anticipates that 15% of the world's elderly will have a mental health concern in 2023, and that number will climb as the population ages [1].

Ageing, social isolation, decreased independence, and long-term health issues worsen mental health, a major concern in geriatric care. Exercise has a

positive effect on mental health in older persons. Regular exercise has been demonstrated to improve mental health in several studies. In their meta-analysis, [2] revealed that geriatric exercise significantly decreases anxiety and sadness.

Physical activity has many mental health benefits. Increased endorphins improve sleep, self-esteem, and social connections. [3] Found that aerobic exercise reduced depressive symptoms in older adults as well as medicine.

Physical activity and mental health

Figure 1: Physical activity and Mental Health (Source:[4])

Significance of the Study: The psychological benefits of exercise have been extensively investigated, but how these effects vary by socioeconomic status is unknown. Socioeconomic factors including income, education, and recreational facilities might affect physical activity and mental health. Higher-income seniors may have better access to gyms and other safe locations to exercise, as well as other physical and mental health services. This study examines seniors' physical activity and mental health across socioeconomic categories to fill that knowledge gap. The study examines how socioeconomic status influences physical exercise and mental health to provide a more comprehensive picture. This information is needed to build community-based activities and public health strategies to improve senior mental health across socioeconomic groups.

Objective

- To study the association between senior adults' physical activity and mental health.
- To examine the impact of socioeconomic status on seniors' physical activity and mental health.
- To determine if exercise affects mental health in seniors by socioeconomic status.

The Importance of Mental Health in Senior Citizens: Mental health as people age is crucial for public health. Depression, anxiety, and cognitive deterioration increase with age. According to the [5, 6], chronic sickness, limited autonomy, and social isolation are increasing older people's mental health concerns. About 7% of seniors have depression, and anxiety disorders are also widespread. Mental health issues reduce physical health, social involvement, and mortality, lowering quality of life.

The Role of Physical Activity in Enhancing Mental Health: Physical activity improves older mental health. Exercise reduces depressed, anxiety, and cognitive decline symptoms. A meta-analysis by [7] found that physical activity programmes improve older depressed adults. [8] discovered that aerobic and resistance training improves older adults' mood and mental health. Physical activity enhances mental health through endorphin generation, better sleep, and social interaction. [9] Found that aerobic exercise had the same antidepressant effect as pharmaceuticals in older adults, emphasising the relevance of physical activity in mental health care.

Socio-Economic Factors and Their Impact on Physical Activity and Mental Health: Physical activity and mental health are strongly influenced by socioeconomic position. [10] Observed that lower socioeconomic groups are less likely to be physically active due to a lack of resources, an unsafe environment, and few recreational facilities. [11] Found that low-income seniors were more depressed and had less physical activity.

Higher SES groups have easier access to gym memberships, personal trainers, and wellness programmes, which can harm mental and physical health [12]. Exercise has well-documented advantages for mental health, but more research is needed to discover whether and how socioeconomic factors affect these benefits.

Researchers have mainly overlooked socioeconomic class to analyse larger groups. For instance, socio-economic variables must be studied in relation to physical activity and mental health. Current research often ignores socio-economic aspects when assessing physical activity treatment accessibility and efficacy. To bridge these gaps, this study

examines seniors' physical activity and mental health outcomes across socioeconomic groups, which may lead to more effective and customised therapies.

Methods

Study Design: This retrospective study examines the association between physical activity and mental health in seniors from varied socioeconomic backgrounds. After reviewing prior data, researchers can determine if physical exercise is linked to mental health outcomes, answering their study questions with less work and no new data.

Sample Size: 150 senior citizens.

Selection Criteria

- Participants must be 60 years of age or older.
- Community-dwelling seniors who are able to provide informed consent and participate in surveys or assessments.
- Seniors with severe cognitive impairments or physical disabilities that prevent participation in physical activities or the completion of mental health assessments will be excluded from the study.

Sampling Method: Participants will be chosen using Convenience Sampling. This technique seeks participants with time and interest in the study. We will recruit from local health clinics, senior citizen societies, and community centres.

Data Collection Methods: Data collection was conducted over a period of three months. Trained research assistants collected height and weight measurements, and participants completed the dietary questionnaires and food diaries.

Medical records were accessed with appropriate permissions to retrieve historical data on BMI and other relevant health information.

Data Analysis: Statistical tools will be used to examine the relationships between socioeconomic status, mental health, and physical exercise. The Pearson correlation coefficient will reveal the amount and direction of the linear link between physical activity and mental health variables. We will use multiple regression analysis to test the hypothesis that physical exercise improves mental health after correcting for socioeconomic status and other confounding factors. ANOVA will also be used to compare mental health outcomes across socioeconomic groups.

We may utilise follow-up t-tests for pairwise comparisons. These analyses will show how socioeconomic position and physical activity affect seniors' mental health.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Demographic Detail of Participants

Demographic Characteristic	Category n	%
Total Participants	150	100.0%
Age		
60-64 years	45	30.0%
65-69 years	50	33.3%
70-74 years	30	20.0%
75-79 years	15	10.0%
80 years and older	10	6.7%
Gender		
Female	82	54.7%
Male	68	45.3%
Socio-Economic Status		
Low	50	33.3%
Middle	50	33.3%
High	50	33.3%
Monthly Income		
Below \$500	50	33.3%
\$500 - \$1000	50	33.3%
Above \$1000	50	33.3%
Educational Background		
High School or Less	50	33.3%
Some College	50	33.3%
Bachelor's Degree or Higher	50	33.3%
Employment Status		
Retired/Unemployed	100	66.7%
Part-time Employed	30	20.0%
Full-time Employed	20	13.3%

Table 1 outlines the demographics of the 150 elderly study participants. The sample's age distribution shows 33.3% 65-69 and 30.0% 60-64. With 54.7% female and 45.3% male participants, the study is gender balanced. This ratio lets us study the association between physical activity and mental health in both sexes.

No socioeconomic tendencies are apparent; 33.3% are low, middle, or high. A third of the sample makes less than 500 rupees per month, another third between 500 rupees and 1,000 rupees, and the remaining third over 1,000 rupees. Income distribution is consistent across the sample.

This distribution covers a wide variety of income and socioeconomic backgrounds, making mental health and physical activity comparisons easier. One-third of participants have a high school education or less, one-third has some college, and one-third have a bachelor's degree. This education gap highlights probable links between education, mental health, and exercise.

Most participants (66.7%) are retired or unemployed, which is typical for seniors. Twenty percent (20.0%) work part-time, whereas 13.3% work full-time. This life stage-specific distribution allows the study of potential relationships between employment status, physical exercise, and mental health.

In conclusion, the demographic makeup ensures a statistically valid sample of seniors to study socioeconomic status, mental health, and physical activity.

Due to its balanced age and gender distribution and diverse socioeconomic origins, the sample is ideal for examining the effects of physical exercise on mental health across socioeconomic groups.

Levels of Physical Activity and Mental Health Status

Table 2: Physical Activity Levels and Mental Health Assessments

Measure	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)	Description
Physical Activity Levels			
Minutes of Moderate-Intensity Activity	150 mins	45 minutes	Average physical activity per week
Physical Activity Categories			
High Physical Activity			30% of participants
Moderate Physical Activity			40% of participants
Low Physical Activity			30% of participants
Mental Health Assessments			
Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS)	6.3	3.2	Mild depressive symptoms
General Anxiety Disorder 7 (GAD-7)	5.8	2.9	Mild anxiety
WHO-5 Well-being Index	14.2	5.1	Moderate level of well-being

Table 2 summarises the 150 older participants' physical activity and mental wellbeing. On average, participants exercised 150 minutes a week at a moderate intensity (standard deviation 45 minutes). According to the data, 30% were very active, 40% moderately active, and 30% very sedentary.

On the Geriatric Depression Scale (GDS), a mean score of 6.3 (SD = 3.2) indicated mild depression. The WHO-5 Well-being Index shows moderate health for the aged, with a mean score of 14.2 (SD = 5.1).

These findings suggest that most people have moderate anxiety and depression but moderate health.

Correlation Analysis

Correlation between Physical Activity and Mental Health Measures:

We calculated Pearson correlation coefficients to study exercise and mental health. Physical activity levels were negatively correlated with depression symptoms ($r = -0.45$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that persons with fewer depressed symptoms are more active. This suggests that as anxiety levels fall, physical activity increases. Positive correlation exists between physical exercise and well-being, with higher levels indicating better mental health ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Correlation between Physical Activity Levels and Mental Health Measures

Measure	Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Physical Activity vs. GDS	-0.45	<0.001
Physical Activity vs. GAD-7	-0.38	<0.001
Physical Activity vs. WHO-5	0.42	<0.001

Socio-Economic Group Comparison

Differences in Physical Activity and Mental Health across Socio-Economic Groups

Physical activity levels varied significantly by socioeconomic category, $F(2, 147) = 5.67, p = 0.004$. The Tukey HSD test for post hoc comparisons showed that the high socio-economic group was substantially more active than the low socio-economic group ($p = 0.002$).

Middle class and impoverished and middle class and well-off were similar. Analysis of variance showed substantial socioeconomic differences in depression symptoms ($F(2, 147) = 3.98, p = 0.02$). Post hoc analysis showed that low-income people were more

likely to have depressed symptoms ($p = 0.03$). Middle class and impoverished and middle class and well-off were similar. An analysis of variance showed substantial socioeconomic anxiety differences ($F(2, 147) = 4.56, p = 0.01$). In post-hoc testing, low-income participants had considerably higher anxiety levels than high-income participants ($p = 0.01$).

Socioeconomic position was similar in the middle and upper classes. Happiness levels varied significantly by socioeconomic category, $F(2, 147) = 4.29, p = 0.02$. High-income people were happier than low-income people, according to Tukey's HSD test ($p = 0.02$). Socioeconomic position was similar in the middle and upper classes.

Table 4: Socio-Economic Group Comparisons for Physical Activity and Mental Health Measures

Measure	Socio-Economic Groups Compared	F-value	p-value
Physical Activity Levels	Low vs. High	5.67	0.004
Geriatric Depression Scale	Low vs. High	3.98	0.02
General Anxiety Disorder 7	Low vs. High	4.56	0.01
WHO-5 Well-being Index	Low vs. High	4.29	0.02

Discussion: Participants averaged 150 minutes of moderate-intensity exercise per week, meeting the WHO's 2020 recommendation for older adults. The results demonstrate that 30% of seniors were very active, 40% moderately active, and 30% very inactive, revealing their physical activity patterns.

Table 5: Comparison of the Present Study with Existing Research

Study	Study Design	Sample Size	Findings
Present Study	Retrospective Cross-Sectional	150	Higher physical activity associated with lower depressive symptoms and anxiety, and better overall well-being across socio-economic groups. Significant socio-economic disparities in physical activity levels and mental health outcomes.
Study 1 [13]	Randomized Controlled Trial	156	Regular physical exercise significantly reduced depressive symptoms among older adults; exercise was as effective as medication for treating major depressive disorder.
Study 2 [14]	Meta-Analysis	1,125	Physical activity had a moderate effect in reducing symptoms of depression and anxiety in older adults. Various forms of exercise (aerobic, resistance, and combined) were effective in improving mental health outcomes.
Study 3 [15]	Observational Study	1,000	Socio-economic factors significantly influenced physical activity levels and mental health outcomes.

This study compares physical activity's impact on older mental health to previous research, which found both parallels and differences. Study 1 found that exercise reduces depressive symptoms in older adults, supporting the current study's findings.

Socioeconomic gaps in physical exercise and mental health provide a new dimension to this investigation. It concluded that socio-economic determinants affect physical activity and mental health, unlike Study 2, which focused on exercise versus depression medication, and Study 3 which did a broad meta-analysis.

This study adds to the data by revealing that seniors' socioeconomic situation considerably affects their

physical activity and mental health outcomes, presenting a more complex picture of how these factors affect seniors' mental health. This study adds socio-economic variables to our understanding of physical exercise and mental health, filling a gap in the literature.

Socio-Economic Factors

The study found different physical activity and mental health results by socioeconomic status. Wealthier elders had better mental and physical health. This study supports previous findings that income, education, and employment status affect older adults' physical activity and mental health. Higher socioeconomic groups may have more

access to fitness clubs, personal trainers, and other leisure activities, explaining these discrepancies. Additionally, they may receive better mental health and social services. To reduce socioeconomic inequality, targeted efforts are needed. Community-based activities can help varied socioeconomic groups connect by offering free or low-cost physical activity and mental health support.

Strengths and Limitations

The study's merits include its holistic approach to assessing physical activity and mental health in a broad population of elderly people. The study included 150 persons for statistical analysis and to examine any correlations between exercise and psychological well-being. There are disadvantages to these benefits.

Due to the study's cross-sectional methodology, determining a cause-and-effect relationship between exercise and psychological well-being is difficult. A longitudinal study is needed to understand how exercise affects mental health over time.

Second, self-reported physical activity and mental health symptoms may be under- or over-reported. Future research could utilise activity trackers to assess physical activity and clinical interviews to assess mental health.

Future Research Directions

Future research should use longitudinal designs to clarify the link between older physical activity and psychological well-being. Research may also compare the mental health benefits of aerobic exercise, strength training, and other physical activities. More research is needed to promote low-income seniors' mental health and physical exercise.

Conclusion

This study concludes that older persons' mental health improves with physical activity, with more exercise and less anxiety and depression. Higher socioeconomic position was connected with greater mental health and physical exercise, showing significant socioeconomic inequalities in the study.

Our findings suggest that elderly people, particularly those from low-income families, need targeted physical activity initiatives to improve mental health. Future research should examine more intervention alternatives to better understand the long-term effects of physical exercise on mental health in different socioeconomic circumstances.

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